

Synthesis, spectral, characterization, catalytic and biological studies of new Ru^{II} N₂O Schiff base complexes

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Abstract : Complexes of the type [RuCl(CO)(B)(L)] (B = PPh₃, AsPh₃, py or pip; L = monobasic tridentate Schiff base) have been synthesized by the reaction of equimolar amounts of [RuHCl(CO)(EPh₃)₂(B)] and Schiff bases in benzene. The resulting complexes have been characterized by analytical and spectral (IR, electronic, NMR) data. An octahedral structure has been assigned to all these complexes. The new complexes have been exhibit catalytic activity for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol and cyclohexanol in the presence of *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide as co-oxidant.

Keywords : Synthesis, Schiff base complex, Ru^{II}.

Introduction

The chemistry of ruthenium complexes with nitrogen containing ligands has been extensively studied in recent years¹. Ruthenium(II) complexes have served as a selective antimetastatic agents², as anticancer drugs against³⁻⁵ colorectal tumors. Here the interactions between ruthenium complexes have gained interest in a number of complexes of adenine⁶, hypoxanthine^{7,8} and guanine^{9,10}. These derivatives have been structurally described in which nitrogen coordination is most frequently observed.

Transition metal complexes of ruthenium have proved to be useful catalyst in many reactions such as oxidation, hydrogenation, carbonylation and hydroformylation by virtue of the accessibility of ruthenium in different oxidation states and ease of coordination with different ligands¹¹⁻¹³. Tridentate Schiff base ligands have been successfully used in several catalytic asymmetric reactions^{14,15}.

Metal complexes of ruthenium containing triphenylphosphine or arsine, nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms are found to be effective catalysts for oxidation reactions^{16,17}. In particular, the selective oxidation of alcohols into carbonyl compounds by metal complexes are well documented in the literature¹⁸⁻²⁰. Sharples *et al.*²¹ carried out a yield based study on oxidation of geranial, etc., catalyzed by ruthenium in the presence of *N*-

methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide (NMO) and *N,N*-dimethylaniline-*N*-oxide. There are very few reports available on the oxidation of carbonyl compounds by using NMO as co-oxidant²². In this area of research Schiff base containing nitrogen and oxygen/sulphur donor ligands have been widely studied²³. The Schiff base transition metal complexes have been extensively studied in recent years owing to their pharmacological properties²⁴⁻²⁸. Schiff base ligands have been extensively investigated with respect to their numerous applications in organic synthesis as well as in pharmacology. In this present work, we report the synthesis, spectroscopy and catalytic activities of ruthenium(II) tridentate Schiff base complexes containing triphenylphosphine/arsine. The general structure of the Schiff base ligands used in this study is given in Fig. 1.

R	Name	Abbreviation
H	Salicylanilidine- <i>o</i> -phenylenediamineacetanilide	Hsalphac
CH ₃	Salicylanilidine- <i>o</i> -phenylenediaminepropylenilide	Hsalphpro
C ₆ H ₅	Salicylanilidine- <i>o</i> -phenylenediaminemethylbenzanilide	Hsalphben

Fig. 1. General structure of the Schiff base ligands.

Results and discussion

Light and air stable ruthenium(II) complexes of the general formula $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{B})(\text{L})]$ (B = PPh_3 or AsPh_3 or py or pip; L = monoanion of tridentate Schiff base) have been prepared by reacting $[\text{RuHCl}(\text{CO})(\text{EPh}_3)_2(\text{B})]$ with the respective Schiff bases in 1 : 1 molar ratio in benzene.

All the complexes are green in colour. The analytical data obtained for the new complexes (Table 1) agree very well with the proposed molecular formulae in all of the above reactions. The Schiff bases behaved as mononegative tridentate ligands. The new products obtained from the reaction of $[\text{RuHCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_3]$ with Schiff base ligands

contained two triphenylphosphine on ruthenium ion, whereas the corresponding reactions of $[\text{RuHCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ or $[\text{RuHCl}(\text{CO})(\text{pip})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ with Schiff base ligands yielded new complexes with only one triphenylphosphine ligand on ruthenium ion. These observations indicate a more labile nature of Ru-P bond compared to the Ru-N bond of the heterocyclic nitrogen bases to the ruthenium ion. The difference in the strength of Ru-P and Ru-N bonds may be explained on the basis of better σ donating ability of the nitrogen bases compared to that of triphenylphosphine.

IR spectral studies :

The $\nu(\text{OH})$ band originally found in the Schiff base ligands disappeared on complexation indicating deprotonation of the phenolic hydroxyl group and coordination of phenolic oxygen to the metal. This is further supported by the shift in the stretching frequency of the phenolic C-O to the higher side by $30\text{--}40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ²⁹. A strong band was observed at $1620\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligand which is characteristic of the azomethine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ group. It is expected that coordination of nitrogen to the metal atom might reduce the electron density in the azomethine link and thus the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching frequency in the complexes was observed in the region $1585\text{--}1599\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating coordination of the Schiff bases through azomethine nitrogen³⁰. In addition, other characteristic bands due to PPh_3 and AsPh_3 are also present around 1435 cm^{-1} ³¹. In the spectra of Schiff base complexes, a medium intensity band observed in the 1020 cm^{-1} region characteristic of the coordinated pyridine or piperidine³². In all the new ruthenium complexes the band due to terminally coordinated to $\text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ group appeared at $1900\text{--}1944\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ³³.

Electronic spectral studies :

The electronic absorption spectra of all the complexes in dichloromethane showed three to four bands in the region $260\text{--}780\text{ nm}$. All the ruthenium complexes are diamagnetic, indicating the presence of ruthenium in the +2 oxidation state. The ground state of ruthenium(II) in an octahedral environment is $^1A_{1g}$ from the t_{2g}^6 configuration, and the excited states corresponding to the $t_{2g}^6 e_g^1$ configuration are $^3T_{1g}$, $^3T_{2g}$, $^1T_{1g}$ and $^1T_{2g}$. Hence, four bands corresponding to the transition $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ are possible in the order of increasing energy.

Table 1. Analytical data of Ru^{II} complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Found (Calcd.) (%)		
		C	H	N
1.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphac})]$	56.02 (56.04)	4.21 (4.2)	(4.21) (4.20)
2.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphac})]$	52.32 (51.28)	3.93 (3.51)	3.93 (3.64)
3.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{salphac})]$	72.0 (71.93)	4.66 (4.62)	3.0 (2.98)
4.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{pip})(\text{salphac})]$	71.88 (70.87)	4.65 (4.11)	3.16 (2.99)
5.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$	61.85 (59.18)	4.12 (3.91)	4.12 (3.87)
6.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$	56.19 (56.21)	3.85 (3.79)	3.99 (3.89)
7.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{salphpro})]$	78.17 (78.16)	4.56 (4.57)	3.42 (3.41)
8.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{pip})(\text{salphpro})]$	78.04 (77.01)	4.55 (3.17)	3.57 (2.18)
9.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphben})]$	64.77 (64.76)	3.77 (3.75)	4.04 (4.3)
10.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphben})]$	60.91 (58.17)	3.55 (3.51)	3.80 (3.67)
11.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{salphben})]$	62.71 (62.69)	4.57 (4.56)	4.12 (4.13)
12.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{pip})(\text{salphben})]$	76.57 (76.52)	4.54 (4.49)	4.07 (4.3)

The bands around 779–589 nm and 485–406 nm are assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and charge transfer (CT) transitions respectively^{34,35} and are listed in Table 2. The charge transfer bands observed in all the complexes due to $M \rightarrow L$ transitions are possible in the visible region^{35–37}. Moreover, the presence of carbonyl, triphenylphosphine/arsine and heterocyclic bases as ligands, which are capable of

plexes of $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$ and $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$ an extra singlet was found in the region at 2.05 ppm, which has been assigned to the extra methyl group present in the Schiff base. The azomethine proton signals in the complexes lie in the 8.0–8.65 ppm range. The peak due to the azomethine showed a high field shift compared to the free Schiff base after complex-

Table 2. IR and electronic spectral data of Ru^{II} complexes

Sl. no.	Complex/ligand	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (cm^{-1})	λ_{max} (nm)
	Hsalphac	1600	1343	-
	Hsalphpro	1620	1336	-
	Hsalphben	1610	1345	-
1.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphac})]$	1586	1303	747, 410, 346, 280
2.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphac})]$	1597	1311	739, 402, 281
3.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{salphac})]$	1584	1311	780, 412, 327, 286
4.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{pip})(\text{salphac})]$	1583	1308	695, 417, 320, 280
5.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$	1586	1307	748, 410, 337, 270
6.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$	1585	1306	740, 406, 260
7.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{salphpro})]$	1587	1305	741, 416, 320, 275
8.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{pip})(\text{salphpro})]$	1533	1306	695, 407, 318, 270
9.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphben})]$	1598	1309	697, 406, 336, 260
10.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphben})]$	1592	1306	680, 402, 340, 270
11.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{salphben})]$	1597	1345	720, 410, 343
12.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{pip})(\text{salphben})]$	1586	1310	737, 417, 340, 265

producing strong ligand field in e_g^* , are in relatively higher energy levels. Therefore the lowest charge bands due to the excitation of an electron from the metal t_{2g} level to an unfilled π^* molecular orbital of the ligand appeared in the relatively high energy region compared due to $t_{2g} \rightarrow e_g^*$ transitions^{36–38}. The other high intensity bands in the 344–269 nm region were characterised by ligand-centered (LC) bands and have been designated as $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transitions for the localized on the azomethine group of the Schiff's base³⁷. The patterns of the electronic spectra of all the complexes indicated the presence of an octahedral environment around the ruthenium(II) ion, similar to that of ruthenium(II) octahedral complexes that have been reported elsewhere³⁹.

${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectral studies :

The ligand to metal bonding is further supported by the ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra (Table 3). All the complexes showed multiplets at 7.0–7.99 ppm range due to the phenyl protons of Schiff base and triphenylphosphine⁴⁰. In the com-

plexes of $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$ and $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$ an extra singlet was found in the region at 2.05 ppm, which has been assigned to the extra methyl group present in the Schiff base. The azomethine proton signals in the complexes lie in the 8.0–8.65 ppm range. The peak due to the azomethine showed a high field shift compared to the free Schiff base after complex-

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Catalytic studies :

The oxidation of benzyl alcohol and cyclohexanol using the different ruthenium complexes as catalyst in the presence of *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide (NMO) as co-oxidant were carried out in dichloromethane. The results of the catalytic oxidation by ruthenium(II) complexes are

Table 3. ^1H NMR and ^{31}P NMR spectral data of Ru^{II} complexes

Sl. no.	Complexes	^1H NMR (ppm)	^{31}P NMR (ppm)
1.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphac})]$	7.0–7.92 (m, aromatic) 8.42 (s, CH=N) 1.6 (s, CH_3)	28.72
2.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$	7.3–7.99 (m, aromatic) 8.62 (s, CH=N) 1.6 (s, CH_3)	<i>a</i>
3.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphben})]$	2.08 (s, CH_3) 7.2–7.89 (m, aromatic) 8.61 (s, CH=N) 1.58 (s, CH_3)	28.65
4.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{salphac})]$	7.3–7.89 (m, aromatic) 8.56 (s, CH=N) 1.53 (s, CH_3)	<i>a</i>
5.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$	7.43–7.90 (m, aromatic) 8.52 (s, CH=N) 1.56 (s, CH_3)	<i>a</i>
6.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphac})]$	2.02 (s, CH_3) 7.2–7.93 (m, aromatic) 8.4 (s, CH=N) 1.8 (s, CH_3)	28.70

a - Not recorded.Table 4. Catalytic oxidation of alcohols by Ru^{II} complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Substrate	Product ^a	Yield ^b	Turnover ^c
1.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphac})]$	Benzylalcohol	A	80.7	83.7
		Cyclohexanol	K	53.6	54.1
2.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphac})]$	Benzylalcohol	A	72.6	74.6
		Cyclohexanol	K	49.6	40.6
3.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{salphac})]$	Benzylalcohol	A	77.6	78.1
		Cyclohexanol	K	41.6	42.1
4.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{pip})(\text{salphac})]$	Benzylalcohol	A	79.7	80.1
		Cyclohexanol	K	43.6	44.1
5.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$	Benzylalcohol	A	73.1	74.8
		Cyclohexanol	K	44.1	45.1
6.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphpro})]$	Benzylalcohol	A	76.6	77.1
		Cyclohexanol	K	40.1	41.2
7.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{salphben})]$	Benzylalcohol	A	84.1	85.1
		Cyclohexanol	K	44.9	45.6
8.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{salphben})]$	Benzylalcohol	A	74.1	77.6
		Cyclohexanol	K	40.1	41.2
9.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{salphben})]$	Benzylalcohol	A	77.6	79.1
		Cyclohexanol	K	42.6	43.1

^aA : Benzaldehyde; K : cyclohexanone. ^bYields based on substrate. ^cMoles of product per mole of catalyst.

summarised in Table 4. Benzaldehyde was formed from benzyl alcohol and cyclohexanol was converted into cy-

clohexanone after 3 h of stirring at room temperature. The aldehyde/ketone formed were quantified as their 2,4-

dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives. In no case was there any detectable oxidation of alcohols in the presence of *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide alone without the ruthenium complexes. All the synthesised ruthenium complexes were found to catalyse the oxidation of alcohols to aldehydes/ ketones but the yields and the turnover were found to vary with different catalysts. The relatively higher product yield obtained for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol than for cyclohexanol is due to the fact that the α -CH moiety of benzyl alcohol is more acidic than in cyclohexanol⁴³. It has also been found that triphenylphosphine complexes possess higher catalytic activity than the triphenylarsine complexes⁴⁴. This may be due to the higher donor ability of the arsine ligand compared to that of phosphines. It has also been found that ruthenium(II) complexes derived from 4 (*N*) methyl phenylenediamine ligands showed less catalytic activity when compared to other complexes, which could be attributed to the presence of the electron donating methyl group in these complexes which decrease the catalytic activity by increasing the electron density on the metal ion⁴⁵.

Antibacterial studies :

The *in vitro* antibacterial screening of the ligands and their ruthenium complexes have been carried out against *Escherichia coli*, *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Salmonella typhi* using a nutrient agar medium by disc diffusion method. The results (Table 5) showed the complexes ex-

hibit moderate activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Salmonella typhi*. The toxicity of ruthenium chelates increase on increasing the concentration⁴⁶. The increase in the antibacterial activity of the metal chelates may be due to the effect of the metal ion on the normal cell process. A possible mode of the toxicity increase may be considered in light of Tweedys chelation theory⁴⁷. Chelation considerably reduces the polarity of the metal ion because of partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups and possible π -electron delocalization over the whole chelate ring. Such chelation could enhance the lipophilic character of central metal atom, which subsequently favours its permeation through the lipid layers of cell membrane. Furthermore, the mode of action of the compounds may involve formation of a hydrogen bond through the azomethine ($>C=N$) group with the active centers of cell constituents, resulting in the interference to normal cell processes⁴⁸. Though the complexes possess activity they could not reach the effectiveness of the standard drug *Streptomycin*. The variation in the effectiveness of the different compounds against different organism depend either on the impermeability of the cells or the microbe of difference in ribosome of microbial cells⁴⁹.

Thus, based on the analytical, spectral (IR, electronic, ¹H NMR and ³¹P NMR) data the following octahedral

Table 5. Antibacterial activity of ligands and ruthenium(II) complexes

Ligand/complex	Diameter of inhibition zones (mm)								
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>			<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>			<i>Salmonella typhi</i>		
	0.25 %	0.5 %	1 %	0.25 %	0.5 %	1 %	0.25 %	0.5 %	1 %
Hsalphac	9	10	12	10	11	12	8	11	12
[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(salphac)]	10	12	14	12	16	19	12	15	19
[RuCl(CO)(AsPh ₃)(salphac)]	11	14	15	14	17	20	13	15	20
[RuCl(CO)(pip)(salphac)]	13	15	18	14	17	20	15	17	19
Hsalphace	9	11	13	8	11	13	9	10	12
[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(salphace)]	11	14	20	10	13	15	13	14	18
[RuCl(CO)(AsPh ₃)(salphace)]	13	16	19	12	18	20	15	16	18
[RuCl(CO)(pip)(salphace)]	14	17	21	14	20	22	19	20	22
[RuCl(CO)(py)(salphace)]	15	18	20	15	17	21	20	21	22
Hsalphben	10	12	13	11	13	14	9	11	12
[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(salphben)]	12	14	17	14	16	18	15	18	20
[RuCl(CO)(AsPh ₃)(salphben)]	14	18	20	15	18	20	17	18	21
[RuCl(CO)(pip)(salphben)]	16	17	21	15	17	21	20	22	23
[RuCl(CO)(py)(salphben)]	17	18	20	16	18	20	20	23	24
<i>Streptomycin</i>	22	23	28	21	27	29	29	21	25

structure (Fig. 2) has been tentatively proposed for all new ruthenium(II) complexes.

R = H, CH₃ or C₆H₅; B = PPh₃, EPh₃, py or pip

Fig. 2. Ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

The Schiff bases were prepared in 80–90% yield by condensation of two mole equivalents of salicylaldehyde, phelylenediamine and respective aldehyde or ketone by following the reported procedure⁵⁰. All the reagents used were of chemically pure grade. Solvents were purified and dried according to the standard procedures⁵¹. RuCl₃·3H₂O, purchased from Loba Chemie, was used without further purification. The starting complexes [RuHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₃]⁵², [RuHCl(CO)(AsPh₃)₃]⁵³, [RuHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂(py)]⁵⁴ and [RuHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂(pip)]⁵⁴ were prepared by reported literature methods.

Physical measurements :

The analysis of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were performed on a Carlo Erba 1160 and a model 240 Perkin-Elmer CHN analyzer at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, India. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets in the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ region in a Nicolet Avater model FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Systronic 119 UV-Vis spectrophotometer using CH₂Cl₂ solution. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Burker 400 MKz instrument using TMS as an internal reference.

Preparation of the new Schiff base Ru^{II} complex :

All the new complexes were prepared by the following general procedure. To a solution of [RuHCl(CO)-(PPh₃)₂(B)] (where B = PPh₃, py (or) pip) and [RuHCl(CO)(AsPh₃)₃] (100 mg; 0.10–0.13 mmol) in benzene the

appropriate Schiff base (39–53 mg; 0.10–0.13 mmol) was added and heated under reflux for 5 h. The resulting solution was concentrated to ca. 3 cm³ and cooled. Light petroleum (60–80 °C) (5 cm³) was then added whereupon the complex separated out. The solid was filtered off, washed and recrystallized from CH₂Cl₂/light petroleum ether mixture and dried *in vacuo*.

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